

INGLIZ TILIDAGI HAJVIY SHE'RLARNING QOFIYA XUSUSIYATI

Boboyev Temur,
Uzswlu doctoral student

Annotatsiya

Ingliz tili adabiyotida ham she'riyat o'ziga xos sistema hisoblanadi. Undagi har bir til birligi o'z ma'nosi va vazifasiga ega. She'rning qofiya xususiyati ham she'riy til sistemasidagi elementlardan biri sifatida o'zining shakli va ifodasiga ega hisoblanadi.

Kalit so'zlar: qofiya, ritm, alliteratsiya, assonans

Аннотация

Поэзия – уникальная система в английской литературе. Каждая языковая единица в нем имеет свое значение и функцию. Рифмованность стихотворения также рассматривается как один из элементов поэтической языковой системы, имеющий свою форму и выражение.

Ключевые слова: рифма, ритм, аллитерация, ассонанс.

Annotation

Poetry is a unique system in English literature. Each linguistic unit in it has its own meaning and function. The rhyming of a poem is also considered as one of the elements of the poetic language system, which has its own form and expression.

Key words: rhyme, rhythm, alliteration, assonance

The rhyme, which has its own form, type and content, becomes richer in terms of content by conveying emotional and expressive connotations in the composition of the poem. The rhythm of the poem, phonetic phenomena and rhyme are important in expressing these connotative meanings. In English, as in other languages, there is no clear definition of the concept of rhyme. Usually,

poetry experts emphasize that rhyme is positional and functional. According to English literary experts, there are about 40 types of rhyme depending on the rhyming of sounds, accentuation, and the type of syllables. Rhyme based on rhythm is classified according to the placement of stress in the word and the size of the syllable. There are the following types of rhyme in English poetry: End (Perfect) rhyme-complete rhyme, internal rhyme-internal rhyme, masculine rhyme, feminine, triple, imperfect rhyme-imperfect rhyme and eye rhyme-similar but different in pronunciation there are types such as rhyme. In perfect rhyme, the last words in the verses of the poem rhyme completely with each other. In this type of rhyme, the most important feature is not the exact sameness of the words, but also the acoustic aspects of the sounds and their recursion. The unique feature of the words that make up the rhyme in the English poems is that the written form, acoustic and articulatory aspects of the words in this language are different. For example, we can see this situation in the following limerick.

*There was an old **Sir**,
Who had a donkey called **Per**.*

Although the words sir [sə:] and per [pə:] look different in these verses, they have the same acoustic properties in pronunciation. The main reason for this is their phonetic-phonological characteristics. According to the rule of correct spelling of the pronounced words in English phonetics, they are written according to the transcription rule. Therefore, words that are different in form a mutual rhyme because they are pronounced the same according to the transcription rule. In English phonetics, when analyzing vowels according to the rule of types of syllables, words in the III-type syllable have a vowel+r; As a result of pronunciation in the form of long [ə:], the words rhymed with each other. The words sir [sə:] and per [pə:] are clear examples of this. The words used in the following lines form a rhyme. Also, in these verses, the vowels -o- and -a- have formed an assonans phenomenon in harmony with each other.

*It had a long **neck**,*

*Sir saw it as a **heck***

The words neck and heck at the end of the lines correspond to the complete rhyme, which is sometimes called perfect rhyme, that is, the words at the end of the line form a complete rhyme with each other. Complete rhyme in English poems means that the sentences in the verse are complete. Short humorous poems in the English language are usually called nursery rhymes, and they are actually created as a result of examples of folklore, historical events or political processes. Below, the political process is satirized in the comic poem created by the people who were dissatisfied with his politics during the reign of Prince George IV, but the effects of laughter can be seen in the poem due to the rhyming of the words in the verses.

*Georgy Porgy pudding a **pie**,*

*Kissed the girls and make them **cry**.*

*When the boys came out to **play**,*

*Georgy Porgy ran **away**.*

This comic poem is about the prince's bad behavior, his revenge on food and women, and negative vices are satirized. The words "pie", "cry", "play" and "away" in the lines of the poem form a rhyme in AABB style. This poem is an end rhyme (full rhyme) according to the type of rhyme. The words "porgy", "pudding" and "pie" in the first line form the alliteration. It can also be seen that the sounds [i] and [e] have formed a phenomenon of mutual assonance. In relation to the hero, his hatred for food and women is shown through the sentences "pudding a pie" in the first line of the poem and "kissed the girls" at the beginning of the second line. The presence of four accented words in each verse of the poem creates a rhythm in the poem, creates an equal amount between the words, and plays an important role in creating a rhyme. The phenomenon of alliteration is also considered a stylistic device in English poetry, which helps to provide musicality in the lines of the poem. Usually, the author implements his ideas in harmony with the melody and

accompaniment. Alliteration has existed in English poetry for a long time, and in poetry it was considered not only as a repetition of sounds, but also as a means of expressing the meanings of words. Alliteration is also found in proverbs and phraseological units in English literature. For example, Last but not least (instead of conclusion). The reason why alliteration is common in English poems, proverbs and phrases is that most of the words in English are based on dynamic stress.

*Goosey Lucy, with a gait so **giggly**,*

*Tripping through the town, she'd make the old men **wiggly**.*

*Her antics were an antidote to any **sorrow**,*

*In her wake, the wisest smiles would **follow**.*

It is also known from the above example that the phenomenon of alliteration is mainly found in fast utterances in languages. In this poem, you can find alliteration sounds in each line. In the first line, the letter [g] creates alliteration in the words "Goosey", "gait" and "giggly", and in the second line, the letter [t] has alliteration in the words "Tripping", "through" and "the town". In the third and fourth lines, the letters [a] and [w] formed alliteration. Characteristically, there is an equal number of alliteration occurrences in each line. In the text of the poem, the importance of the sounds in the formation of mutual rhyme is the same, and as a result of the dynamic emphasis being equally distributed to the words in each line, certain rhyming is formed.

References

1. https://www.poetrysoup.com/poem/goosey_lucy_1679946
2. <https://www.songsforteaching.com/nurseryrhymes/georgieporgie.php>
3. Muhammed N. A stylistic study of Limericks, College of Education, 2014

4. Леонтьева И. К вопросу об английской рифме (на примере творчества Уистена Хью Одена)// Язык художественной литературы, Москва, 2011, с 7-17

